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Comparison of Four Popular International Indicators to Identify Digital Divide

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Abstract

There is a broad consensus among researchers and economic decision-makers that digitalization is important, but that the tools for measuring it are not uniform across regions of the world. As a result, the perception of the digital development of different regions or even companies may differ, and identifying the phenomenon of digital divide itself is not a simple task. Accordingly, the aim of this research is to compare and evaluate international indicators that can be used to identify digital divide and to make recommendations for the development of indicator systems. The research compares and draws conclusions from key indicators in Europe and Southeast Asia. The Digital Economy and Society Index, the Digital Index, the Digital Intelligence Index and the Digital Integration Index show that digital development can be assessed along a number of dimensions and indicators. Although the intent of each index is similar, the methodologies differ on how to measure digital divide, and the conclusions on which benchmark is the best are partly contradictory. However, they all have in common that a conscious effort must be made to overcome the digital divide. Identifying and accurately measuring the digital divide is not an easy task, which is why there is currently no universally accepted indicator to capture all the factors of this complex phenomenon. This will need to be determined by future research.

JEL classification: O 11, O 33, O 38

Keywords: DESI, industry 4.0, digital transformation, inequality, global development

1. Introduction

As digital technologies have become the cornerstone of modern economies, it is increasingly important to assess and understand the state of digital transformation at the global, national, and regional levels (Borowiecki et al., 2021, Sati, 2024). Digitalization touches upon various aspects, including infrastructure, access to digital services, digital skills, innovation, and governance. To capture this multi-dimensional phenomenon, several indices have been developed, each providing unique insights into a country or region's digital progress and competitiveness (Stankovic et al., 2021).

The primary goal of this research is to examine and evaluate key indices that measure digitalization, such as the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI), the Digital Intelligence Index (DII), the ASEAN Digital Integration Index (ADII), and the DiGiX index, among others. These indices serve as tools for decision makers, businesses, and researchers alike, offering a standardized method for comparing how different countries or regions are adapting to the challenges and opportunities brought by digital transformation. Each index focuses on different aspects of digitalization, from infrastructure and digital skills to digital economy readiness and societal integration of digital technologies (European Commission, 2021).

One of the central questions this working paper addresses is how these indices have evolved over time to reflect the rapid changes in the digital landscape. For instance, early indices like the Information Society Index (ISI) or the E-Readiness Index (ERI) primarily focused on basic ICT infrastructure and internet access. However, as digital technologies have become more pervasive, more recent indices like DESI and DII incorporate factors like innovation capacity, the integration of digital technologies into businesses, and the impact of digitalization on society

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and governance. This evolution demonstrates that measuring digitalization is not a static process but one that must adapt to reflect the broader implications of digital technologies on economies and societies (European Commission, 2021).

Through a detailed analysis of these indices, this research explores both their strengths and limitations. On one hand, most of the indices provide a broad view of digitalization, assessing various dimensions like digital skills, connectivity, and the digital economy (Aissaoui, 2022; Lythreatis et al., 2022). On the other hand, some may not fully capture the nuanced cultural, political, or economic contexts of certain regions, potentially oversimplifying or overlooking key factors that influence digital transformation (Cilan et al., 2009; Vicente & Gil-de-Bernabé, 2010). This working paper critically evaluates the methodologies behind these indices, assessing how well they reflect the true state of digitalization in the countries or regions they aim to measure.

Another important focus of this research is the impact of digitalization on economic growth, innovation, and social development. The ability to measure digital progress is crucial not only for policymakers but also for businesses and educational institutions, as it allows them to identify areas for improvement and investment. Indices like DiGiX emphasize the importance of digital skills and innovation in fostering a competitive economy. By analyzing these indices, this research highlights how digitalization is linked to broader economic and societal trends, such as the Fourth Industrial Revolution, which is fundamentally changing the nature of work, production, and consumption (Marti & Puertas, 2023). In addition to exploring global indices, the research also examines regional efforts to measure digitalization. For example, the ASEAN Digital Integration Index (ADII) provides a region-specific framework for understanding the progress of digital integration within Southeast Asia, highlighting unique challenges and opportunities faced by ASEAN countries (Ali & Faroque, 2023). Similarly, the DESI index provides a detailed analysis of the digital economy within the European Union, offering a closer look at how different EU member states are performing in terms of digital infrastructure, public services, and business integration (European Commission, 2021). By comparing these regional indices with global indices, the research underscores the importance of contextual factors in shaping digital progress (Hidalgo et al., 2020).

The study concludes by discussing the future of digital measurement and the potential for new, more refined indices to emerge as digital technologies continue to evolve. As technologies like artificial intelligence, blockchain, and the Internet of Things (IoT) become more embedded in economies and societies, future indices will need to adapt to capture the full scope of digital transformation (Usman et al., 2024). Furthermore, the research emphasizes the need for a more holistic approach to measuring digitalization, one that not only accounts for technological factors but also considers the social, cultural, and political dimensions of digital change (Van Dijk, 2020).

In summary, this working paper provides an overview of how digitalization is measured, offering a critical evaluation of existing indices and their methodologies. By examining indices such as DESI, DiGiX, ADII, and DII, the research highlights both the progress made in measuring digital transformation and the challenges that remain. Ultimately, it underscores the importance of accurate and contextualized measurements in guiding policy decisions, fostering innovation, and promoting economic and social development in the digital age.

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2. History of indices measuring digitalization to identify digital divide

The rapid advancement of digital technologies has transformed global economies, societies, and governance, making the measurement of digitalization a critical aspect of understanding how nations and organizations adapt to and harness these technological changes (OECD, 2021). Over the years, various indicators and indices have been developed to assess the progress of digital transformation across different regions, sectors, and aspects of society.

Measuring digitalization serves multiple purposes. It helps to identify gaps in infrastructure, skills, and services and allows for informed decisions on resource allocation and policy interventions (Rogers, 2016). For businesses, these measurements provide valuable insights into market potentials and competitive landscapes. In academia and research, digital indicators are essential for understanding the correlation between digital progress and economic or social development. Indices also provide a standardized framework for benchmarking countries or regions in order to promote international collaboration and competition. The evolution of these measurements reflects the dynamic nature of the digital economy, with indices adapting over time to account for new technologies and their impacts.

Table 1.

Popular indicators of the digital economy, in chronological order of introduction.

Introduction	Short	Full name	Organization	countries	indicators
1997	ISI	Information Society Index	IDC	53	< 20
2000	ERI	E-Readiness Index	EIU	70	< 100
2001	TAI	Technology Achievement Index	UNDP	72	< 10
2002	EGDI	E-Government Development Index	UNPAP	182	< 10
2002	IDI	ICT Development Index	ITU	154	< 20
2002	NRI	Networked Readiness Index	WEF	148	< 80
2003	DAI	Digital Access Index	ITU	178	< 10
2003	IS	Infostates	ORBICOM	183	< 20
2005	KEI	Knowledge Economy Index	KEI	140	< 20
2005	DOI	Digital Opportunity Index	ITU	181	< 20
2005	ICT-OI	ICT Opportunity Index	ITU	183	< 20
2006	ICT-DI	ICT Diffusion Index	UNCTAD	180	< 10
2014	DESI	Digital Economy and Society Index	EU	28	< 40
2019	DiGiX	Digital Index	BBVA	100	20
2019	GCI 4.0	Global Competitiveness Index 4.0	WEF	141	103
2020	DII	Digital Intelligence Index	Fletcher	90	160
2021	ADII	ASEAN Digital Integration Index	ASEAN	15	30
2022	GII	Global Innovation Index	WIPO	132	81
2022	WDC	World Digital Competitiveness Ranking	IMD	63	54

Source: Compiled from Moroz (2017), with additional research.

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The history of measuring digitalization can be traced back to the late 1990s with the emergence of the first indices (Table 1). One of the earliest efforts was the Information Society Index (ISI), introduced by IDC in 1997. It covered 53 countries and provided a basic framework for assessing a nation's capacity to participate in the digital economy. In 2000, the E-Readiness Index (ERI) from EIU expanded on this concept, measuring how ready countries were to adopt internet-based technologies across 70 nations. Similarly, the Technology Achievement Index (TAI), introduced by UNDP in 2001, focused on technology development's role in shaping economic opportunities and societal progress (Szabó, 2024).

As the 2000s progressed, more specialized indices were introduced, reflecting different dimensions of the digital transformation. For example, the E-Government Development Index (EGDI) was launched by UNPAP in 2002, and the ICT Development Index (IDI) in 2003, which was among the first to focus specifically on the growth of information and communication technologies (ICT), covering 154 countries. The Networked Readiness Index (NRI) by WEF in 2002 and the Digital Access Index (DAI) in 2003 further highlighted the importance of technological infrastructure and access to digital services. By 2003, indices like the Knowledge Economy Index (KEI) and the Digital Opportunity Index (DOI) emphasized the growing role of knowledge, innovation, and opportunities driven by digitalization, acknowledging the importance of human capital in this evolving landscape.

As we entered the 2010s, newer indices like the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI), introduced by the European Union in 2014, and DiGiX, developed by BBVA in 2016, began capturing a broader view of the digital transformation (European Commission, 2021). These indices not only measured ICT infrastructure but also examined societal, economic, and cultural impacts of digitalization, making them crucial tools for assessing the digital readiness of regions like the European Union. In more recent years, the Global Competitiveness Index 4.0 (GCI 4.0) by WEF, introduced in 2019, shifted focus to how countries adapt to the Fourth Industrial Revolution, emphasizing digital skills, innovation, and ICT infrastructure (Ali & Faroque, 2023). Likewise, the Digital Intelligence Index (DII) by Fletcher, which debuted in 2020, aimed to measure the maturity and integration of digital technologies across global economies.

In Asia, the ASEAN Digital Integration Index (ADII), launched in 2021, marks a significant effort to assess the region's progress in digital integration (Isono & Prilliadi, 2023). Global indicators such as the Global Innovation Index (GII) and the World Digital Competitiveness Ranking (WDC), both of which assess innovation potential and competitiveness in a highly digitalized world, continue to be pivotal in providing comprehensive global overviews (Hidalgo et al., 2020).

Over time, the development of digital indicators has expanded in both scope and complexity. These indices reflect the transformative power of technology on society, economies, and governance. From the early days of measuring basic ICT infrastructure to today's multidimensional indices that assess readiness for the Fourth Industrial Revolution, these tools remain invaluable for tracking global digital progress and guiding policy decisions (OECD, 2021). By analyzing these indices, stakeholders can better understand the current state of digitalization and identify areas for further development and innovation (European Commission, 2021).

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3. Digital divide

Digital underdevelopment is a significant challenge for many nations, where lack of access to technology, digital infrastructure, and education limits both economic growth and social development (OECD, 2001, Cruz-Jesus, Oliveira, & Bacao, 2012). This underdevelopment creates a digital divide, where regions lagging in digital transformation find themselves at a competitive disadvantage in the global economy (Setthasuravich & Kato, 2020). Overcoming digital divide involves a combination of well-targeted policy interventions, investment in infrastructure, and efforts to boost digital literacy and skills (Ragnedda, 2017). Digital indices are important to diagnose the level of digital maturity in different countries and identify areas where improvements are needed (Vicente & Gil-de-Bernabe, 2010). These indices not only measure the current state of digital infrastructure and digital skills but also serve as benchmarks to prioritize investment and reform, ensuring that digital development is inclusive and equitable.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) plays a crucial role in overcoming digital divide by enabling scalable solutions for education, infrastructure deployment, and personalized digital experiences. AI can enhance user knowledge by tailoring digital learning platforms to meet the specific needs of individuals, making it easier for people in underdeveloped regions to acquire digital skills. Additionally, AI can be used to optimize the development and deployment of digital infrastructure, ensuring that resources are allocated efficiently and that regions with the greatest need receive prioritized attention. Furthermore, AI-driven algorithms can predict and monitor digital adoption rates, helping policymakers adjust their strategies to accelerate digital transformation (McKinsey & Company, 2023). Importantly, AI can also raise public awareness about the importance of digital skills and inclusion, by running targeted campaigns that encourage greater participation in digital economies and services. By utilizing data from digital indices such as DESI and ADII, alongside AI's predictive capabilities, nations can make more informed decisions about how to overcome digital divide (Isono & Prilliadi, 2023). AI not only aids in the development of digital infrastructure but also supports the creation of an inclusive digital environment where every citizen has the opportunity to benefit from advancements in technology (Ali & Faroque, 2023). In this way, digital indices and AI complement each other to create a roadmap for countries striving to bridge the digital divide and promote long-term economic and social growth (Hidalgo et al., 2020).

4. Comparison of DESI, ADII, DII and DiGiX

4.1 Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI)

In today's increasingly digitized world, understanding the dynamics of the digital economy and society has increased importance. The Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) stands as a comprehensive tool developed by the European Commission to measure and track the progress of European Union (EU) member states in their digital transformation journey (European Commission, 2021). DESI is designed to capture various dimensions of the digital economy and society, providing insights into the state of digitalization across EU countries. It consists of four main dimensions: Connectivity, Human Capital, Integration of Digital Technology, and Digital Public Services. These dimensions are composed of a wide array of indicators, ranging from broadband infrastructure and digital skills to e-commerce usage and e-government services (Figure 1.).

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Figure 1.
Digital Economy and Society Index (2022)

Source: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/desi>

Connectivity assesses the quality and reach of broadband infrastructure, including internet speed and mobile network coverage. Human Capital measures the digital skills of the population, focusing on basic and advanced digital competencies essential for participating in the digital economy (European Commission, 2021). Integration of Digital Technology evaluates the adoption and utilization of digital tools by businesses, such as e-commerce, cloud services, and digital workflows (Borowiecki et al., 2021). Digital Public Services examines the availability and efficiency of online government services, including e-government initiatives and digital public sector innovations (European Commission, 2023).

Each dimension is assessed through a set of relevant indicators, weighted according to their importance. This methodology ensures an extensive evaluation of digital performance while allowing for comparisons across countries and over time (European Commission, 2021). DESI is a powerful aid for policymakers to monitor their country's digital performance, identify strengths and weaknesses, and formulate policies to foster digitalization. By highlighting areas needing improvement, DESI facilitates targeted interventions to enhance digital infrastructure, promote digital skills development, and stimulate digital innovation and entrepreneurship.

Moreover, DESI contributes to supplementing a competitive digital single market within the EU by fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing among member states. It enables decision-makers to learn from best practices and successful strategies implemented by leading digital performers, promoting convergence in digital development across the region (European Commission, 2021).

DESI also has importance in monitoring the progress of EU countries towards achieving the objectives set in the Digital Single Market Strategy and the European Digital Agenda. It provides regular updates on key digital indicators, enabling them to track advancements and adjust policies accordingly to ensure alignment with overarching digital policy goals (European Commission, 2021).

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4.2 ASEAN Digital Integration Index (ADII)

In the context of the ASEAN region's rapid digitalization, the ASEAN Digital Integration Index (ADII) was created to assess and monitor digital integration among member states. The ADII is a composite index developed to measure the level of digital integration within the ASEAN region. Its primary pillars include digital infrastructure, digital economy, digital government, digital society, and digital innovation (Figure 2). Each pillar is assessed through a set of indicators carefully selected to capture key aspects of digital integration (Isono & Prilliadi, 2023). The digital infrastructure pillar evaluates broadband penetration, mobile network coverage, and ICT accessibility. The digital economy pillar examines e-commerce adoption, digitalization of supply chains, and online payment systems. The digital government pillar assesses the availability of e-government services and digital governance policies. The digital society pillar looks at digital literacy, internet usage, and inclusiveness of digital technologies. Finally, the digital innovation pillar measures R&D investment, tech hubs, and innovation adoption (ASEAN, 2019).

Figure 2.
ASEAN Digital Integration Index (2020)

	 Pillar 6 Institutional & Infrastructural Readiness					
ASEAN	55.27	62.81	58.84	48.21	49.32	62.85
Australia	90.72	90.77	88.00	52.99	66.30	60.87
China	86.50	75.73	74.73	64.76	68.74	53.63
Japan	93.36	90.93	82.00	54.77	77.32	60.67
New Zealand	92.04	85.91	90.33	55.70	65.84	63.90
South Korea	89.28	88.42	81.42	53.77	77.92	63.59

Source: <https://asean.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/ADII-Report-2021.pdf>

By providing extensive information on digital integration, the ADII provides help for governments, businesses, and stakeholders in advancing digital development across ASEAN member states. The ADII is a valuable tool for policymakers and governments to benchmark their country's digital integration progress, identify areas for improvement, and formulate targeted strategies to boost digital development. By providing comparative insights into digital performance across ASEAN member states, the ADII supports peer learning and knowledge exchange, fostering collaboration and synergies in digital initiatives (ASEAN, 2019).

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The ADII contributes to advancing the ASEAN Digital Integration Framework and the ASEAN Digital Masterplan 2025 by tracking progress towards achieving digital integration objectives. It enables legislators to observe the implementation of digital policies and initiatives, identify bottlenecks, and make efforts to address challenges hindering digital integration (ASEAN, 2019). Furthermore, the ADII plays a crucial role in promoting regional competitiveness and economic resilience by fostering a digitally connected ASEAN community. It aids cross-border digital trade, investment, and collaboration, unlocking new opportunities for businesses and entrepreneurs to thrive in the digital economy (Isono & Prilliadi, 2023). As ASEAN continues its journey towards digital transformation, the ADII remains essential in navigating the complexities of the digital age and driving sustainable digital growth.

4.3 The Digital Intelligence Index (DII)

The Digital Intelligence Index (DII) is a comprehensive framework designed to measure the digital economy and digital competitiveness of various countries. Developed by the Fletcher School at Tufts University in partnership with Mastercard, the DII evaluates the digital ecosystem and the environment that fosters digital innovation and adoption (Figure 3.). It is structured around four primary pillars: Supply Conditions, Demand Conditions, Institutional Environment, and Innovation and Change. Each of these pillars enclose a wide range of indicators that collectively provide an insight of a country's digital capabilities and readiness. (Na-Nan et al., 2020)

Figure 3.
Digital Intelligence Index in the studied countries (2020)

Source: <https://digitalintelligence.fletcher.tufts.edu/dei>

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The DII is further divided into different components and clusters, enabling an analysis of specific areas within the digital landscape. For instance, under the Supply Conditions pillar, the index examines the infrastructure and resources available to support digital growth, including internet access and speed, technological infrastructure, and digital literacy. Demand Conditions focus on the behaviour and preferences of consumers and businesses, assessing aspects such as e-commerce activity, online engagement, and digital skills among the population. The Institutional Environment pillar evaluates the regulatory and policy frameworks, including data protection laws, cybersecurity measures, and government support for digital initiatives. Finally, the Innovation and Change pillar measures the dynamism of the digital economy, looking at startup activity, research and development expenditure, and the presence of tech hubs and innovation clusters (Chakravorti et al., 2020).

The DII applies a variety of indicators to quantify these dimensions, such as broadband penetration rates, mobile internet usage, e-government services, and digital financial inclusion. These indicators are derived from reputable sources like the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), World Bank, and other global datasets, ensuring the index's reliability and accuracy. The collected data is then normalized and aggregated to produce composite scores for each country, allowing for comparative analysis across different regions and economic contexts (Chakravorti et al., 2020).

4.4 The Digitization Index (DiGiX)

The Digitization Index (DiGiX) is an extensive framework designed to assess and monitor the extent of digitization across countries. It is developed by BBVA Research and it evaluates the digital transformation by examining six key dimensions: Infrastructure (Figure 4.), Households, Enterprises, Government, Regulation, and Digital Content. Each dimension is composed of a variety of indicators that collectively provide a detailed picture of a country's digital landscape. The infrastructure dimension assesses the quality and reach of physical and technological infrastructure necessary for digital activities, including broadband coverage and mobile network availability (Mammadli & Klivak, 2020).

The Households dimension measures digital access and usage within homes, focusing on internet penetration rates, digital literacy, and household access to ICT. Enterprises are evaluated based on their adoption and integration of digital technologies, examining indicators such as e-commerce activities, digital skills within the workforce, and the extent of digitalization in business processes. The Government dimension measures the extent to which public services are digitized, including e-government initiatives and digital public services. Regulation assesses the policy and regulatory environment that supports digital growth, such as data protection laws and cybersecurity regulations. Finally, Digital Content examines the availability and use of online content and services, including social media usage, online entertainment, and digital information resources (BBVA Research, 2021).

The DiGiX applies a diverse set of indicators within these dimensions to provide a comprehensive evaluation of a country's digital maturity. For example, indicators for Infrastructure might include broadband penetration rates and average internet speeds, while those for Households might assess the percentage of households with internet access and levels of digital literacy. Enterprise indicators may evaluate the proportion of businesses engaging in

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online sales and the prevalence of digital skills training. (Mammadli & Klivak, 2020). Government indicators might cover the availability of online public services and the extent of digital transactions in public administration. Regulatory indicators include assessments of data protection policies and the robustness of cybersecurity measures. Digital Content indicators can encompass the volume and diversity of online content consumed, social media engagement, and access to digital media (BBVA Research, 2021).

Figure 4.
Digital Index (2019, 2020 és 2022)

Source: <https://www.bbva.com/en/publicaciones/digix-2022-update-a-multidimensional-index-of-digitalization/>

The DiGiX supports tracking digital progress, identifying gaps, and formulating strategies to enhancing digital development. By providing a detailed analysis of digital indicators, the index facilitates cross-country comparisons and helps stakeholders understand the factors driving digital transformation. Policymakers use the insights from DiGiX to design targeted interventions aimed at improving digital infrastructure, enhancing digital skills, and fostering an inclusive digital economy. Businesses leverage the index to inform their digital strategies and market entry decisions, while researchers utilize it to study digital trends and their socio-economic impacts (Katz et al., 2014).

4.5 Comparison of indicators

DESI focuses on EU member states, while ADII targets ASEAN countries. Both indices aim to benchmark digital performance, yet they differ in regional focus and specific metrics. DESI emphasizes EU's digital transformation, facilitating targeted policy interventions and fostering collaboration among member states. In contrast, ADII aims to promote regional digital integration in ASEAN by evaluating digital infrastructure, economy, government, society, and innovation. DII and DiGiX provide broader assessments, covering various countries worldwide.

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The DII evaluates the digital ecosystem and environment that fosters digital innovation and adoption. DiGiX focuses on infrastructure, households, enterprises, government, regulation, and digital content, offering a detailed picture of a country's digital landscape.

When comparing these indices, several similarities and differences emerge. Digital skills are one of the areas of overlap. DESI, ADII, and DiGiX all evaluate digital competencies among the population, although they differ in their specific measures. DESI focuses on ICT graduates and digital skills levels (At least basic digital skills and above basic digital skills), ADII on graduates in STEM fields, and DiGiX on digital literacy among households (Digital skills among population, Individuals using the internet).

Business adoption of digital technologies is evaluated by both DESI and ADII, though their metrics differ. DESI measures the integration of digital technology in business processes, while ADII assesses innovation and entrepreneurship. Despite the differing indicators, both indices aim to capture the extent of digital tool adoption by enterprises.

Digital public services are assessed by DESI, ADII, and DiGiX, with each index evaluating the availability and efficiency of online government services. DESI and ADII also measure the digitization of public services for citizens and businesses (Digital public services for citizens (DESI), Digital public services for business indicator (DESI), Availability of government services indicator (ADII)), reflecting the importance of e-government in digital transformation. Regulatory environments are considered by DiGiX and DII (E-participation index (DiGiX), E-government development index (DII)), both of which evaluate data protection laws and cybersecurity measures. These indices highlight the role of supportive policy environments in fostering digital growth and ensuring security in the digital space.

Both DESI and DiGiX assess fixed broadband infrastructure and internet accessibility, reflecting their importance in digital transformation. with indicators such as DESI's Overall fixed broadband take-up and DiGiX's Fixed (wired)-broadband subscription. Similarly, DII's Fixed broadband subscriptions per 100 inhabitants indicator measures comparable aspects of broadband accessibility.

Mobile connectivity is another common focus, with DESI, DiGiX, and DII all including indicators for mobile broadband subscriptions (Mobile broadband take-up (DESI), Active mobile-broadband subscriptions (DiGiX), Active mobile-broadband subscriptions per 100 inhabitants (DII)). These measures reflect the increasing importance of mobile devices in providing digital access and facilitating engagement.

When it comes to the security of internet services, DiGiX's Secure internet services indicator is similar to DII's Secure internet servers (per 1 million people) indicator, reflecting a shared emphasis on the availability and reliability of secure internet infrastructure. These indicators are important in assessing a country's cybersecurity framework, which is essential for protecting digital transactions and data integrity.

Next, ADII's Legal framework indicator aligns closely with DiGiX's indicators on the Legal framework's adaptability to digital business models, the Efficiency of the legal framework in challenging regulations, and the Efficiency of the legal framework in settling disputes. Similarly, it parallels DII's indicators on the Efficiency of the legal framework in settling disputes and the Adaptability of the legal framework to digital business models. As we can see,

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this is the first case during the comparative analysis to find exact matches in different indicators. These comparisons underscore the critical role of a supportive and agile legal environment in enabling digital transformation. By ensuring that legal systems are capable of addressing the complexities of the digital economy, these indices emphasize the need for regulatory frameworks that can effectively manage technological advancements and digital business operations.

In summary, while each index offers a unique perspective on digital transformation, they share common goals of measuring digital infrastructure, skills, technology integration, public services, and regulatory environments. On the other hand, they approach the measurement of digital advancement in a very different way, which can be recognised in the diversity of the composition of indicators. By comparing these indices, we can gain understanding of the digital divide and identify best practices and strategies for supporting digital development across different regions and contexts.

4.6 Comparison of measurement

Table 2.

Country results of the examined indices

OVERALL SCORES	Benchmark countries			Southeast Asian countries			European countries			
	Denmark	Finland	Singapore	Thailand	Indonesia	Malaysia	Hungary	Poland	Slovakia	Montenegro
DigiX 2022 (0-1)	1,00	0,90	0,93	0,58	0,57	0,74	0,51	0,64	0,55	0,51
DESI 2022 (0-100)	69,33	69,6	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	43,76	40,55	43,45	n.i.
DII 2021 (0-100) STATE	87,17	87,30	98,82	53,04	47,72	69,03	57,75	63,58	63,01	n.i.
DII 2021 (0-100) MOMENTUM	43,78	38,55	53,79	48,12	64,03	57,27	30,64	57,29	42,29	n.i.
RANKING	Benchmark countries			Southeast Asian countries			European countries			
	Denmark	Finland	Singapore	Thailand	Indonesia	Malaysia	Hungary	Poland	Slovakia	Montenegro
DigiX 2022 (99 countries)	1.	5.	3.	45.	48.	25.	59.	36.	55.	63.
DESI 2022 (28 countries)	2.	1.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	n.i.	22.	24.	23.	n.i.
DII 2021 STATE (90 countries)	5.	4.	1.	48.	58.	26.	41.	34.	35.	n.i.
DII 2021 MOMENTUM (90 countries)	61.	79.	25.	44.	3.	14.	89.	13.	66.	n.i.

Source: Own compilation

To understand the varying results in assessing a country's digital development (Table 2), it has key importance to analyze how each index measures different aspects of digital transformation and how these measurements can lead to divergent outcomes.

DESI focuses on a broad range of factors to provide a comprehensive overview of digitalization in the EU, emphasizing policy-making and implementation to achieve the Digital Single Market. ADII focuses on facilitating digital integration and cooperation among ASEAN countries, emphasizing regional strategies and policies to support digital trade and economic growth. Only very few indicators provide an exact match. Although both indices assess similar aspects like digital skills, and digital services, ADII places a stronger emphasis on regional integration, trade, and specific regulatory frameworks relevant to ASEAN.

Firstly, the regional context and integration goals of the EU and ASEAN play a significant role in shaping their respective indices. The EU has a long history of economic and political integration, with established policies aimed at creating a cohesive internal market.

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Consequently, the DESI focuses on indicators that support the Digital Single Market, such as connectivity, digital skills, internet use, and digital public services. The aim is to ensure that all member states reach a certain level of digital development to enable seamless cross-border digital activities and services. In contrast, ASEAN is a diverse region with varying levels of economic development and digital infrastructure. The ADII aims to promote digital integration and cooperation among its member states, addressing disparities and fostering an environment conducive to digital trade and innovation. Thus, the ADII emphasizes regional integration aspects such as digital trade, cybersecurity, and digital payments, reflecting the need to create a supportive ecosystem for digital economic growth across different national contexts.

Secondly, the economic and digital development levels of the EU and ASEAN are quite different. EU member states generally have more advanced digital infrastructures and higher levels of digital literacy. The DESI indicators build on this foundation, pushing for advanced digital services, high-quality connectivity, and widespread digital skills to maintain competitiveness and innovation within the EU. Conversely, ASEAN countries exhibit a wide range of digital maturity levels, from highly advanced digital economies to those still developing basic digital infrastructures. Therefore, ADII indicators cater to this diversity by focusing on foundational elements such as ICT infrastructure, digital skills development, and regulatory frameworks to speed up digital integration and equal growth opportunities across the region.

Thirdly, the policy and regulatory frameworks of the EU and ASEAN influence the design of their digital indices. The EU has a strong focus on regulatory harmonization and ensuring a common digital market. Consequently, DESI includes indicators that monitor the implementation and effectiveness of EU-wide regulations and policies, such as e-government services and digital technologies' integration in businesses. On the other hand, ASEAN prioritizes creating a conducive environment for digital trade and innovation, recognizing the different regulatory landscapes of its member states. Hence, ADII indicators focus on areas like digital trade logistics, data protection, and cybersecurity to ensure that regional policies support digital businesses and cross-border trade.

Finally, the strategic objectives of the EU and ASEAN shape the focus of their digital indices. DESI aligns with the EU's strategic objectives involves removing digital barriers and enhancing the digital capabilities of all member states. The emphasis is on comprehensive digital transformation across various sectors and ensuring that all EU citizens benefit from digital advancements. On the other hand, ADII aligns with ASEAN's strategic objectives of fostering economic integration and enhancing regional cooperation in the digital economy. The focus here is on creating synergies between member states to boost digital trade, protect data, and encourage innovation, while also addressing the digital divide within the region.

Moving onto DiGiX, it considers factors like digital demand, supply, institutional frameworks, and innovation capabilities. It provides a broad, global perspective, whereas DESI is narrowly tailored to support EU policy-making and integration. DiGiX and ADII both measure digital readiness but in different regional contexts. DiGiX's global scope encompasses a wide variety of economic and technological environments, using a standardized approach to compare countries. ADII, by contrast, is specialized for the ASEAN region, with indicators designed to address regional digital integration, trade facilitation, and regulatory environments.

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ADII focuses on specific needs like digital payments and logistics, reflecting ASEAN's priorities in enhancing intra-regional digital connectivity and economic collaboration. DiGiX and the Digital Intelligence Index (DII) both assess digitization but with different emphases. DiGiX provides a broad overview of digital demand, supply, and institutional environments worldwide. DII focuses more on the evolution and sustainability of digital ecosystems, emphasizing factors such as digital adoption, institutional support, and the development of digital trust. DII's approach is more dynamic, looking at how digital capabilities grow and evolve over time, whereas DiGiX offers a more static snapshot of current digital conditions.

The DII evaluates digital evolution and trust, providing a composite look at the progress and sustainability of digital ecosystems globally. This contrasts with DESI's specific aim of monitoring digital development within the EU. It stands out for its focus on digital evolution and trust, offering valuable insights into how digital ecosystems develop and sustain themselves. However, DII's strengths also highlight its complexities. The index's detailed approach to assessing digital evolution and trust can make it more challenging to interpret, especially for stakeholders looking for straightforward metrics. Reliable data on trust and digital evolution is also harder to obtain, which can affect the accuracy and comprehensiveness of the index. Moreover, DII's emphasis on these areas might overshadow other critical aspects such as regulatory environments and practical infrastructure developments.

This contrasts with DESI's specific aim of monitoring digital development within the EU. While DESI tracks connectivity, skills, and digital services to promote EU-wide policy objectives, DII focuses on the broader dynamics of digital growth and the establishment of trust in digital systems. DII defines how countries build and maintain digital infrastructures and services over time, a perspective not covered by the more narrowly focused DESI.

DII's global perspective on digital evolution and trust differs from ADII's regional focus on ASEAN. ADII's indicators are tailored to enhance digital cooperation and integration among ASEAN countries, focusing on practical aspects like digital trade and cybersecurity. DII, however, looks at the broader picture of digital maturity, considering how countries worldwide develop and sustain digital ecosystems. DII's emphasis on the trajectory of digital development and the cultivation of digital trust provides a different analytical angle compared to ADII's focus on regional integration.

While DESI, ADII, DiGiX, and DII each provide valuable contributions to understanding digital progress, they also have notable limitations. DESI's EU-specific focus and discontinuation, ADII's challenges with regional diversity and missing innovation metrics, DiGiX's broad but static global scope, and DII's complex and trust-focused methodology each highlight areas needing improvement. Additionally, all indices could benefit from more comprehensive coverage of digital entrepreneurship, societal impacts, and dynamic tracking of technological changes. These critiques underscore the need for continuous adaptation and enhancement of digital indices to remain relevant and effective in a rapidly evolving digital world.

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4.7 The need for a new measurement dimension

Introducing a "growth potential" indicator into existing digital development indices, such as the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI), ASEAN Digital Integration Index (ADII), Digital Intelligence Index (DII), and Digix (Digitization Index), could provide significant insights into a country's future trajectory in the digital economy. This new dimension would specifically focus on investments in digitization as a key driver of potential growth. By assessing investments in digital infrastructure, education, research and development (R&D), and technology adoption, the growth potential indicator would help to identify which countries are most likely to advance rapidly in their digital transformation efforts over the coming years (Brodny & Tutak, 2024).

The rationale for emphasizing investments in digitization as a core component of the growth potential dimension lies in the clear link between financial commitments to digital sectors and the capacity for future development. Countries that are currently making substantial investments in building and upgrading digital infrastructure, enhancing digital skills among the workforce, and fostering innovation through R&D are likely to have a higher capacity for digital growth. These investments are critical for scaling digital solutions, ensuring widespread access to advanced technologies, and maintaining competitiveness in a rapidly evolving global digital landscape (OECD, 2021).

For instance, investment in digital infrastructure, such as expanding broadband networks and enhancing data storage capabilities, directly correlates with improved digital connectivity and accessibility, foundational elements for digital growth. Similarly, funding digital education and training programs is essential for developing a digitally skilled workforce that can adapt to and drive technological advancements. Investments in R&D, particularly in emerging technologies like artificial intelligence (AI) and blockchain, foster innovation and enable countries to develop competitive digital ecosystems (European Commission, 2023).

Including a growth potential indicator based on digitization investment would be particularly useful in highlighting emerging digital economies that may currently have lower levels of digital maturity but are positioned for rapid growth. For example, a country that is significantly investing in 5G technology and digital skills training might score lower on current digital use metrics but could demonstrate high growth potential due to its strategic investments. This dimension would provide a more dynamic and forward-looking perspective, enabling stakeholders to identify not just the current leaders in digital development, but also the future ones.

However, adding such an indicator to the existing indices is not without its challenges. One significant issue is the impact on data comparability over time. The established indices like DESI, ADII, DII, and Digix have been used to assess digital development consistently across various countries and years. Altering these indices to include a new growth potential dimension fundamentally changes the measurement framework, making it difficult to compare new data with older datasets accurately. The inclusion of a new indicator focused on investment in digitization would alter the weighting and interpretation of the indices, leading to changes in country rankings that may not reflect actual shifts in digital development but rather differences in what is being measured.

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Moreover, incorporating a growth potential dimension based on investment data introduces challenges in standardizing measurements. Investment in digitization can vary widely in terms of scope, scale, and the sectors it targets, making it difficult to create a uniform metric that applies across diverse national contexts. The data on digital investments might also be inconsistent or incomplete, particularly in less developed digital economies, thereby affecting the reliability of the growth potential scores (BBVA Research, 2023).

Furthermore, the forward-looking nature of a growth potential indicator, which relies on predicting future development based on current investments, introduces a degree of uncertainty and speculation. Unlike existing indicators that measure tangible outcomes, such as broadband coverage or digital skills levels, growth potential would be based on assumptions about the effectiveness of current investments in producing future digital growth. This could lead to potential overestimation or underestimation of a country's future digital capabilities, thereby complicating policy planning and international comparisons (OECD, 2021).

Additionally, transitioning to a revised index that includes this new dimension would require recalibrating the entire framework and potentially re-educating stakeholders on how to interpret the new results. This would require a transitional period, during which the continuity and comparability of the data could be compromised. Policymakers, researchers, and other stakeholders would need to understand that the revised indices are not directly comparable to older versions due to the changes in the areas being inspected and the introduction of new metrics (European Commission, 2023).

In conclusion, while a growth potential indicator based on investments in digitization could provide valuable insights into the future prospects of digital economies, it also introduces significant methodological and practical challenges. The addition of this dimension would require careful consideration to ensure that the benefits of understanding future digital growth are balanced against the need for consistency and comparability with historical data. Stakeholders must be prepared to address these challenges to leverage the new insights effectively while maintaining the integrity and utility of the indices.

5. Discussions

A significant insight drawn from comparing DESI, ADII, DII, and DiGiX is the diversity in their approaches, which reflects different methodological priorities and regional contexts. For instance, while DESI provides extensive insights specifically tailored to EU member states, ADII focuses on fostering digital cooperation within the ASEAN region. DII, meanwhile, emphasizes digital evolution and trust at a global scale, while DiGiX offers a broader but static view of digital infrastructure and usage. This diversity in focus reveals that no single index can comprehensively capture the entire scope of digital development across varied global contexts.

One of the critical observations is that each index plays a distinct role in guiding policy and fostering digital advancement, but they also face limitations that must be acknowledged. DESI's EU-centric approach has made it a valuable tool for aligning regional policies, but its insights are not as applicable outside of the European context. Similarly, ADII's focus on the ASEAN region means it caters to the unique needs of its member states, which may not be relevant for global application. On the other hand, DII and DiGiX, while offering global coverage, may sacrifice regional specificity that can be crucial for targeted policy measures.

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A recurring theme in these findings is the challenge of data consistency and comparability across indices. Different methodologies and indicator compositions can lead to varying interpretations of a country's digital standing. For example, the DII's focus on trust and adaptability may highlight strengths in governance and institutional support that indices like DESI or DiGiX, with their infrastructure-focused metrics, may overlook. This methodological variability underscores the importance of using a combination of indices for a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of digital progress.

Furthermore, the discussion should consider the implications of these indices for strategic decision-making. While indices like DESI and ADII guide policies within their respective regions, they do not necessarily translate into universal best practices. Policymakers must navigate these indices' strengths and limitations to craft context-sensitive strategies. For instance, while DESI may inform EU member states on enhancing digital public services and infrastructure, countries in other regions with different socio-economic landscapes might need to rely on findings from broader indices like DII or DiGiX for more applicable insights.

The limitations inherent in these indices also open the door for recommendations for future enhancements. One promising area for development is the inclusion of forward-looking indicators that evaluate the potential for growth and future digital advancements. Incorporating metrics that track investments in digital infrastructure, education, and emerging technologies could offer a predictive element, highlighting not only current performance but also a country's trajectory for future digital growth. This addition would be particularly valuable for identifying nations poised to become digital leaders based on their strategic investments.

Moreover, future iterations of these indices could benefit from incorporating a broader perspective that goes beyond traditional technological metrics. Indices that evaluate not just the economic impact of digitalization but also its social and environmental implications would align with global sustainability efforts. Metrics assessing e-waste management, energy consumption, and the societal inclusiveness of digital technologies would provide a more comprehensive picture of digital transformation.

Lastly, the conversation should touch on the potential for cross-index harmonization. A standardized framework for comparing results across different indices could improve their utility and enhance the ability of policymakers to interpret the data within a broader context. Such harmonization would allow for more cohesive insights, facilitating policy coordination at international levels and encouraging best-practice sharing among regions.

In conclusion, while the indices examined in this working paper—DESI, ADII, DII, and DiGiX—each offer valuable insights into digital development, their limitations highlight the need for continual adaptation and methodological refinement. Including predictive, sustainability-oriented, and cross-comparable metrics could enhance the indices' relevance, ensuring they remain robust tools for guiding digital policy and fostering global and regional digital advancements.

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6. Conclusions

The comparative analysis of DESI, ADII, DigiX, and DII underscores the complex nature of measuring the digital divide. Each index offers unique insights but also exhibits distinct limitations. The divergent rankings observed for the same countries across these indices indicate that each index emphasizes different aspects of digital development and integration. Consequently, they recommend varying areas for improvement, reflecting their specific methodological frameworks and indicator sets. This variability underscores the importance of utilizing a combination of indices to obtain a more nuanced and holistic understanding of the digital divide. Policymakers and researchers should consider the strengths and limitations of each index to formulate more effective strategies for bridging the digital divide.

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